

SAINT-VENANT'S PRINCIPLE FOR A GENERALIZED SOLUTION OF A THIRD-ORDER EQUATION AND SOME OF ITS APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

The paper established energy estimates of an analog of the Saint-Venant principle for generalized solutions of third-order equations of composite type. These estimates make it possible to indicate the nature of the zero-seeking solution of the equation in the neighborhood of irregular boundary points. Note that the methodology used in our study can be applied to study the properties of solutions to an odd-order equation of another type.

Keywords: Third-order equation, composite type, irregular boundary points, generalized solution, energy estimates, analog of the Saint-Venant principle, domain with non-smooth boundary.

1. Introduction. It is known that, the points P on the boundary $\partial\Omega$ are called irregular points, if there is no smooth nondegenerate transformation $U \rightarrow R^n$ in any neighborhood U of the point P that translates into a $(n - 1)$ – dimensional ball. Otherwise, the points P is called regular.

Among the numerous approaches to the study of boundary value problems for differential equations in areas with a non-smooth boundary, two main approaches can be distinguished. One of them is the reduction of the boundary value problem to the solution of integral equations (see [1,2,3,4]). The method of solving partial differential equations based on reducing the boundary value problem to integral equations was first used by Radon (see [5]) for the Dirichlet and Neumann problems for the Laplace equation.

Another approach is based on the application of functional methods and energy estimates. In this way, it is possible to obtain the existence and uniqueness theorems of the generalized solution of the problems under study under very weak constraints on the boundary structures (see [6]). The study of the smoothness of the generalized solution is carried out separately inside the domain and in the neighborhood of the boundary. We know that the singularities of solutions of differential equations arise only in the neighborhood of irregular points. The same approach is also associated with the method of studying the properties of generalized solutions in the neighborhood of the boundary, based on the use of energy estimates expressed by the Saint-Venant principle.

Here we present one of the results on the study of the behavior of a generalized solution of a third-order equation of a composite type in the neighborhood of an irregular boundary point, based on the application of energy estimates of the type analogy of the Saint-Venant principle. It should be noted that the level of such studies regarding odd-order equations is at an initial stage.

In the works of O. A. Oleynik and G. A. Iosifyan (see [7,8]), energy estimates of the type of the Saint-Venant principle, which takes into account the change in the shape of the body, are established for generalized solutions of the first boundary value problem. These estimates allowed us to obtain uniqueness theorems for

the solution of the problem in bounded and unbounded domains in the class of functions having an infinite energy integral, as well as results on disposable sets of singularities of the solution on the boundary depending on the characteristics of the domain. The integral of the energy of the solution of the problem over a region excluding the neighborhood of an irregular boundary point either has to grow fast enough as this neighborhood decreases, or it is bounded. The works of O. A. Oleinik and J. Kopáček (see [9, 10]) are a further development of the works [7] and [8]).

The study of solutions of the system of elasticity theory in the neighborhood of the corner points of the boundary and in the vicinity of the edges is devoted to the work [11], [12] and [13].

Consider in the domain $\Omega \subset R_+^n = \{x: x_1 > 0\}$ the equation

$$lAu + Bu = f(x), \quad (1)$$

$$\text{where } lu = l_0u + \alpha(x)u,$$

$$l_0u = \alpha^k(x)u_{x_k},$$

$$Au = a^{ij}(x)u_{x_i x_j} + a^i(x)u_{x_i} + a(x)u,$$

$$Bu = b^{ij}(x)u_{x_i x_j} + b^i(x)u_{x_i} + b(x)u.$$

We break up the bound of Ω . Denote

$$\sigma_0 = \{x \in \Gamma: \alpha^k(x)v_k(x) = 0\},$$

$$\sigma_1 = \{x \in \Gamma: \alpha^k(x)v_k(x) > 0\},$$

$$\sigma_2 = \{x \in \Gamma: \alpha^k(x)v_k(x) < 0\},$$

where $\Gamma = \partial\Omega = \sigma_0 \cup \sigma_1 \cup \sigma_2$,

$v(x) = (v_1(x), v_2(x), \dots, v_n(x))$ is a vector of the inner normal of Ω in the point x .

Here we will consider the following boundary value problem in the domain Ω

$$lAu + Bu = f(x),$$

$$u|_{\sigma_0 \cup \sigma_1 \cup \sigma_2} = 0, \quad l_0u|_{\sigma_1} = 0, \quad (2)$$

We suppose here and later on that the summation is carried out by repeating indexes, all coefficients in (1) and their derivatives are bounded and measurable in any subdomain of the domain Ω . Furthermore, we suppose that boundary of Ω is smooth or piecewise-smooth.

If the domain is bounded, then the existence and uniqueness theorem for solutions of problem (1), (2) was investigated in [14]. If the domain is unlimited, then in the works [15,16,17,18] energy estimates of the type of the Saint-Venant principle were established, which makes it possible to prove the existence and the uniqueness of the solution theorems of the problem (1), (2). Further, in [19, 20], the existence and uniqueness theorems of the solution of problem (1), (2) in unbounded domains are proved. These theorems are proved in the class of functions having an unbounded energy integral depending on the geometric characteristics of the domain. The proof uses the energy estimates of the Saint-Venant principle type established in [15,16,17,18].

Define the operator C :

$$Cu = (b^{ij} + \alpha a^{ij} - \alpha_{x_k}^k a^{ij}) u_{x_i x_j} + (b^i + \alpha a^i - \alpha_{x_k}^k a^i) u_{x_i} + (b + \alpha a - \alpha_{x_k}^k a) u \equiv c^{ij} u_{x_i x_j} + c^i u_{x_i} + cu.$$

We assume that the following conditions will be met for this operator:

$$c^{ij} = c^{ji}, \quad c_0 |\xi|^2 \leq c^{ij} \xi_i \xi_j \leq c_1 |\xi|^2, \quad \text{for all } x \in \Omega \cup \Gamma, \quad \text{for all } \xi \in R^n. \quad (4)$$

Define the quadratic form $d^{ij} \xi_i \xi_j$:

$$d^{ij} = c^{ij} - (\alpha^i a^{kj})_{x_k} + \alpha^i a^j + \frac{1}{2} (\alpha^k a^{ij})_{x_k}.$$

Further, we everywhere imply that

$$\sum_{k=1}^n [\alpha^k(x)]^2 \neq 0, \quad \alpha^1(x) \neq 0, \quad q^{ij} = c - \frac{1}{2} c_{x_i}^i + \frac{1}{2} c_{x_i x_j}^{ij} + \frac{1}{2} (\alpha^i a)_{x_i} \leq -q_0 < 0, \\ d_0 |\xi|^2 \leq d^{ij} \xi_i \xi_j \leq d_1 |\xi|^2, \quad \text{for all } x \in \Omega \cup \Gamma, \quad \text{for all } \xi \in R^n. \quad (5)$$

Let

$$\Omega_{\tau^0} = \Omega \cap \{x : x_1 < \tau^0\}, \quad \Gamma_{\tau^0} = \Gamma \cap \{x : x_1 < \tau^0\}, \\ \sigma_{0,\tau^0} = \{x \in \Gamma_{\tau^0} : \alpha^k(x) v_k(x) = 0\}, \quad \sigma_{1,\tau^0} = \{x \in \Gamma_{\tau^0} : \alpha^k(x) v_k(x) > 0\}, \\ \sigma_{2,\tau^0} = \{x \in \Gamma_{\tau^0} : \alpha^k(x) v_k(x) < 0\}.$$

For some $h > 0$, define

$$\sigma_{1,h,\tau^0} = \{x \in \sigma_{1,\tau^0} : \rho(x, \partial \sigma_{1,\tau^0}) > h\}, \quad \sigma_{1,\tau^0}^h = \sigma_{1,\tau^0} \setminus \sigma_{1,h,\tau^0}.$$

Let $E(\Omega_{\tau^0})$ be a set of functions $v \in C^2(\bar{\Omega}_{\tau^0})$ such that $v = 0$ on Γ_{τ^0} and $l_0 v = 0$ on $\sigma_{0,\tau^0} \cup \sigma_{2,\tau^0} \cup \sigma_{1,\tau^0}^h$ some number $h > 0$.

We denote as $H(\Omega_\tau)$ the Hilbert space obtained by closing with respect to the norm

We know that, boundary value problems have applications in fluid dynamics, astrophysics, hydrodynamic, astronomy, beam and long wave theory and engineering. Boundary value problems of higher order is studied in the works [21,22].

2. Notation and Formulation of the Problem.

Here we will establish energy estimates for the generalized solution of problem (1) (2). These estimates indicate the nature of the vanishing of the function $u(x)$

at an irregular point P of the boundary of the domain Ω , if $f(x) = 0$ in some neighborhood of the point P .

We assume that the operator is uniformly elliptic, i.e. the conditions are satisfied

$$a^{ij} = a^{ji}, \quad a_0 |\xi|^2 \leq a^{ij} \xi_i \xi_j \leq a_1 |\xi|^2, \quad \text{for all } x \in \Omega \cup \Gamma, \quad \text{for all } \xi \in R^n. \quad (3)$$

$$\|u\|_{H(\Omega_{\tau^0})} = \left\{ \int_{\Omega_{\tau^0}} (d^{ij} u_{x_i} u_{x_j} + u^2) dx + \int_{\sigma_{1,\tau^0}} \alpha^k v_k a^{ij} u_{x_i} u_{x_j} ds \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}}.$$

Now consider bilinear form

$$a(u, v) = \int_{\Omega_{\tau^0}} \left[\alpha^k a^{ij} u_{x_i} v_{x_j x_k} + (\alpha^k a^{ij})_{x_j} u_{x_i} v_{x_k} - \alpha^k a^i u_{x_i} v_{x_k} - c^{ij} u_{x_i} v_{x_j} \right] dx + \\ + \int_{\Omega_{\tau^0}} \left[(c_{x_j}^{ij} - \alpha^i a - c^i) u v_{x_i} + (c - c_{x_i}^i + c_{x_i x_j}^{ij}) u v \right] dx.$$

Definition 1. If $u(x) \in H(\Omega_{\tau^0})$ and satisfy the identity

$$a(u, v) = \int_{\Omega_{\tau^0}} f(v) dx \quad (6)$$

for an arbitrary function $v(x) \in E(\Omega_{\tau^0})$, $v|_{S_\tau} = 0$ where $S_\tau = \Omega \cap \{x : x_1 = \tau\}$, then the function $u(x)$ is said to be generalized solution of the equation (1) in the domain Ω_{τ^0} , with boundary conditions $l_0 u|_{\sigma_{1,\tau^0}} = 0$ and $u|_{\sigma_{1,\tau^0} \cup \sigma_{0,\tau^0} \cup \sigma_{2,\tau^0}} = 0$.

3. Energy Inequalities. (Analog of the Saint-Venant principle) Let at set $S_\tau = \Omega \cap \{x : x_1 > 0\}$ any $\tau \in (0, \tau^0)$, $\tau^0 > 0$ not empty and $d^{ij} \xi_i \xi_j > d_{11} |\xi|^2$, $d_{11} = \text{const} > 0$, $q_1^{ij} \leq q_{10} < 0$ for all $x \in \Omega_\tau$, for all $\xi \in R^n$. If function $u(x)$ is generalized solution of the equation (1) in the domain Ω_{τ^0} , with boundary conditions $l_0 u|_{\sigma_{1,\tau^0}} = 0$, $u|_{\sigma_{1,\tau^0} \cup \sigma_{0,\tau^0} \cup \sigma_{2,\tau^0}} = 0$ and $f(x) = 0$ in $\Omega_{\tau^0} = \Omega \cap \{x_1 : x_1 < \tau^0\}$, then for functions $u(x)$ fair assessment

$$\int_{\Omega_{\tau^0}} u^2 \Lambda(x_1) \Phi(x_1, \tau^0, \varepsilon) dx \leq \int_{\Omega_{\tau^0}} E(u) \Phi(x_1, \tau^0, \varepsilon) dx \leq \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \int_{\Omega_{\tau^0}} E(u) dx, \quad (7)$$

where $0 < \varepsilon < 1$, $0 < x_1 < \tau^0$. Here functions $\Phi(x_1, \tau^0, \varepsilon)$ is a solution of the problem

$$\Phi'' = (1 - \varepsilon) \mu(x_1) \Phi, \quad 0 < x_1 < \tau^0, \quad (8)$$

$$\Phi(\tau^0, \tau^0, \varepsilon) = 1, \quad \Phi'(\tau^0, \tau^0, \varepsilon) = 0, \quad (9)$$

$\mu(\tau)$ and $\Lambda(\tau)$ is a continuous functions such that for which the inequality is true

$$0 < \mu(\tau) \leq \lambda(\tau) \equiv \inf_{v \in N} \left\{ \int_{S_\tau} E(v) dx' \left| \int_{S_\tau} P(v) dx' \right|^{-1} \right\}, \quad (10)$$

$$0 < \Lambda(\tau) \leq \inf_{v \in N} \left\{ \int_{S_\tau} E(v) dx' \left| \int_{S_\tau} v^2 dx' \right|^{-1} \right\}, \quad (11)$$

respectively. Here

$$x' = (x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n), \quad P(v) = \alpha^1 a^{i1} v v_{x_i} + \frac{1}{2} \left(c^{11} + \alpha^1 a^1 - (\alpha^1 a^{1j})_{x_j} \right) v^2.$$

moreover, inf is taken for all functions v such that $v \in C^2(\overline{\Omega_{\tau^0}})$, $v = 0$, $l_0 v = 0$ and in $\partial \Omega_{\tau^0}$ and

σ_{1,τ^0} , respectively.

Proof. Assume in (6) $v(x) = u_m(x)(\psi(x_1, \delta) - 1)$, where $\psi(x_1, \delta) = (x_1 - \delta)\Phi_{x_1}(\delta, \tau^0, \varepsilon) + \Phi(\delta, \tau^0, \varepsilon)$ if $0 \leq x_1 \leq \delta$; $\psi(x_1, \delta) = \Phi(x_1, \tau^0, \varepsilon)$, if $0 < \delta < x_1 \leq \tau^0$; $\psi(x_1, \delta) = 1$, if $\tau^0 \leq x_1$.

$$u_m \in E(\Omega_\tau), u \in H(\Omega_\tau), \|u_m - u\|_{H(\Omega_\tau)} \rightarrow 0, \delta = const > 0.$$

Then

$$a(u - u_m + u_m, u_m(\psi - 1)) = 0 \text{ in } \Omega_{\tau^0}.$$

Therefore

$$a(u_m, u_m(\psi - 1)) = \delta_m \text{ in } \Omega_{\tau^0}, \tag{12}$$

where $\delta_m = a(u - u_m, u_m(\psi - 1)) \rightarrow 0$.

It is obvious that $\delta_m \rightarrow 0$ at $m \rightarrow \infty$. Integrating by parts (12), we have

$$\int_{\Omega_{\tau^0}} E(u_m)(\psi - 1)dx \leq \int_{\Omega_{\tau^0} \setminus \Omega_\delta} P(u_m)\psi'' dx + \delta_m.$$

Now we will use the definition functions $\mu(x_1)$ and $\Phi(x_1, \tau^0, \varepsilon)$, i.e. (10), (11). Then we get

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega_{\tau^0}} E(u_m)(\psi - 1)dx &\leq (1 - \varepsilon) \int_{\Omega_{\tau^0} \setminus \Omega_\delta} P(u_m)\mu(x_1)\psi dx + \delta_m \leq (1 - \varepsilon) \int_{\Omega_{\tau^0} \setminus \Omega_\delta} E(u_m)\psi dx + \delta_m \leq \\ &\leq \int_{\Omega_{\tau^0}} E(u_m)\psi dx - \varepsilon \int_{\Omega_{\tau^0}} E(u_m)\psi dx - (1 - \varepsilon) \int_{\Omega_\delta} E(u_m)\psi dx + \delta_m, \\ \int_{\Omega_{\tau^0}} E(u_m)\psi dx - \int_{\Omega_{\tau^0}} E(u_m)dx &\leq \int_{\Omega_{\tau^0}} E(u_m)\psi dx - \varepsilon \int_{\Omega_{\tau^0}} E(u_m)\psi dx - (1 - \varepsilon) \int_{\Omega_\delta} E(u_m)\psi dx + \delta_m. \end{aligned}$$

Hence

$$\varepsilon \int_{\Omega_{\tau^0}} E(u_m)\Phi(\delta, \tau^0, \varepsilon)dx \leq \int_{\Omega_{\tau^0}} E(u_m)dx - (1 - \varepsilon) \int_{\Omega_\delta} E(u_m)\psi dx + \delta_m. \tag{13}$$

The second relation from inequality (7) is obtained from (13) when $\delta \rightarrow 0$ and $m \rightarrow \infty$. The first relation follows directly from the definition function $\Lambda(\tau)$.

Note. In Theorem 1, the function $\Phi(x_1, \tau^0, \varepsilon)$ can be replaced by a function satisfying the initial conditions (9) and the inequalities

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi''(x_1, \tau^0, \varepsilon) &\leq (1 - \varepsilon)\mu(x_1)\Phi(x_1, \tau^0, \varepsilon), \\ \Phi(x_1, \tau^0, \varepsilon) &> 0, \Phi'(x_1, \tau^0, \varepsilon) < 0 \quad 0 < x_1 < \tau^0. \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

Such substitutions make it easier to build a function $\Phi(x_1, \tau^0, \varepsilon)$ in specific cases, i.e. in specific domains.

Now we assume that

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda(x_1) \geq \mu(x_1) = const > 0, \max_{s_\tau} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{2}(c^{11} + \alpha^1 a^1 - (\alpha^1 a^{1j})_x) \right), 0 \right\} &= \gamma(\tau), \\ \max_{s_\tau} (\alpha^1 a^{i1}) &= \beta(\tau). \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

Then, given the conditions (13) and applying the Cauchy-Bunyakovsky and Friedrich's inequality from (10), we have.

$$\left| \int_{S_\tau} P(v) dx' \right| \leq \left| \int_{S_\tau} \alpha^1 a^{i1} v v_{x_i} dx' \right| + \frac{1}{2} \left| \int_{S_\tau} (c^{11} + \alpha^1 a^1 - (\alpha^1 a^{1j})_{x_j}) v^2 dx' \right| \leq$$

$$\leq \beta(\tau) \left[\int_{S_\tau} v^2 dx' \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[\int_{S_\tau} v_{x_i}^2 dx' \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} + \gamma(\tau) \int_{S_\tau} v^2 dx' \leq \left[\frac{\beta(\tau) \lambda_1(\tau)}{\pi d_0} + \frac{\gamma(\tau) \lambda_1^2(\tau)}{\pi^2 d_0} \right] \int_{S_\tau} E(v) dx'$$

So we can put

$$\mu(\tau) = \pi^2 d_0 (\pi \beta(\tau) + \lambda_1^2(\tau) \gamma(\tau))^{-1}. \quad (16)$$

If $\frac{1}{2} (c^{11} + \alpha^1 a^1 - (\alpha^1 a^{1j})_{x_j}) \leq 0$ on S_τ , then $\gamma(\tau) = 0$.

To facilitate the construction of a function $\Phi(x_1, \tau_2)$ in specific domains, we everywhere assume that $\frac{1}{2} (c^{11} + \alpha^1 a^1 - (\alpha^1 a^{1j})_{x_j}) \leq 0$ and $\max \beta(\tau) = \beta_0$. Then $\mu(\tau) = \pi d_0 (\beta_0(\tau) \lambda_1(\tau))^{-1}$.

For a function $\Phi(x_1, \tau^0, \varepsilon)$, we can get estimates that characterize the growth of the function $\Phi(x_1, \tau^0, \varepsilon)$, $x_1 \rightarrow 0$ depending on the behavior of the function $\mu(x_1)$.

Let the domain Ω in the neighborhood of the origin lie inside some angular areas $\{x: |x'| \leq M^2 x_1^2, M = \text{const} > 0\}$. Then according to (16) one can put $\mu(x_1) = \frac{\pi c}{M^2 x_1^2}$. Then the

solution to problem (8), (9) is the function

$$\Phi(x_1, \tau^0, \varepsilon) = \frac{1}{m_1 + m_2} \left[m_2 \left(\frac{x_1}{\tau^0} \right)^{m_1} + m_1 \left(\frac{x_1}{\tau^0} \right)^{-m_2} \right] \quad (16)$$

where m_1 and $-m_2$ are the roots of the equation $m(m-1) = \pi c(1-\varepsilon)M^{-2}$, $m_1 > 0$, and $m_2 > 0$. It is obvious that $\Phi(x_1, \tau^0, \varepsilon) \rightarrow \infty$ when $x_1 \rightarrow 0$.

Now consider the area Ω for which $\lambda_1(x_1) \leq \pi c k^{-1} x_1^{2(k+1)} (k + (k+1)x_1^k)^{-1}$, when $0 < x_1 < \tau^0$

. It's easy to see that $\lambda_1(x_1) \leq \pi c \left(k \frac{1}{2} x_1^{k+1} \right)^2$. For such a domain Ω , according to (15)

$\mu(x_1) \leq 2k x_1^{-2(k+1)} (k + (k+1)x_1^k)$. It is not difficult to check that the function

$\Phi\left(x_1, \tau^0, \frac{1}{2}\right) = \frac{1}{2} [\exp(x_1^{-k} - 1) + \exp(1 - x_1^{-k})]$ satisfies the initial conditions (9) when $\tau^0 = 1$

and the inequalities (12) for $0 < x_1 < 1$, $\varepsilon = \frac{1}{2}$. Then in the estimate (7) we can put

$$\Phi\left(x_1, 1, \frac{1}{2}\right) = \frac{1}{2} [\exp(x_1^{-k} - 1) + \exp(1 - x_1^{-k})].$$

It is obvious that $\Phi(x_1, 1, \varepsilon) \rightarrow \infty$ when $x_1 \rightarrow 0$.

Conclusion. In [21], we established internal local estimates for the generalized solution of equation (1), and then in [22], we established special energy estimates, which is also an analog of the Saint-Venant principle, which can be used to evaluate the generalized solution of equation (1) only in unbounded domains. Using these estimates, inequality (7) allows us to study the behavior of the solution of equation (1) in the vicinity of irregular boundary points.

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